

ISSN 2582-5356
RNI-UPBIL/2018/78084

Special Issue ❖ January - June, 2023
Bilingual (English & Hindi)

UGC CARE Enlisted Journal

KUTAP

AN ENSEMBLE OF MUSICIANS

कुतप

A Peer Reviewed Refereed International Journal

संगीत एवं अन्तर-विषयक विधाओं पर केन्द्रित

Special issue

on

Indian Knowledge System : Nurtient of Science, Society and Culture

Editor

Prof. (Dr.) RENU JOHRI

32.	Indigenous Environmental Knowledge Awareness of Prospective Teachers	153
	<i>Dr. Sojia John</i>	
33.	Empowering Scheduled Caste Women in Higher Education: Indian Knowledge System	159
	and New Education Policy	
	<i>Dr. Sanjay Kumar, Amit Kumar</i>	
34.	Rediscovering the Holistic Essence: Indian Knowledge Systems and NEP 2020	166
	<i>Dr. Deepti Kumari</i>	
35.	Exploring Cultural and Social Dynamics: Impact on Education in Modern Times	170
	<i>Neha Kumari, Dr. Sarika Pandey</i>	
36.	Factors Affecting Sports Participation Among Children	177
	<i>Mr. Sharad Chandra Rai, Dr. Rahul Heeralal Kanojiya, Dr. Bhaskar Shukla</i>	
37.	Qualitative Analysis of Honey Through Melissopalynology	181
	<i>Shraddha Tiwari, P.C. Misra</i>	
38.	Traditional Indian Knowledge Systems: A Holistic Approach to Natural	183
	Resource Management	
	<i>Ravish Sharma, Kash Dev Sharma</i>	
39.	Indigenous knowledge and Traditional healing Practices in Sikkim	188
	<i>Saurav Pradhan</i>	
40.	Iks and Swot Analysis of Transformational Changes in Higher Education Through Nep-2020.....	195
	(With special reference of Varanasi District)	
	<i>Dr. Swarnim Ghosh</i>	
41.	Relevance of Indian knowledge Tradition in Modern context	201
	<i>Dr. Brajesh srivastava</i>	
42.	Nutritional wisdom inherited Bhagavad Gita: In relation to Yoga sadhaka's diet	204
	<i>Dr. Saroj Nain, Dr. Manmeet Kaur</i>	
43.	Promotion of Yoga in Indian Knowledge System: Nourishment in Health and	208
	Physiological Factors	
	<i>Ajaz Sheikh, Dr. Mohammed</i>	
44.	Traditional Knowledge: An Introduction to Ancient Indian Polity & The King.....	212
	<i>Dr. Vineeta</i>	
45.	A SWOT Analysis Framework for Integrating AI in Indian Knowledge System.....	217
	<i>Sonal Linda, Ranjan Kumar</i>	
46.	Indian Knowledge System : Impressions and Influences on Global Culture	226
	<i>Mrs. Pratyashi Saikia Tandon</i>	
47.	Health Benefits of Spices in Indian Food System.....	232
	<i>Manpreet Kaur, Dr. Suman Bala</i>	

Iks and Swot Analysis of Transformational Changes in Higher Education Through Nep-2020

(With special reference of Varanasi District)

Dr. Swarnim Ghosh*

Abstract : If we talk about Gandhian Philosophy for educational advancement in higher education, then we clearly see that the structural form of higher education should be such that it can make the future life of the student self-sufficient; such an education system should be developed which can make students self-reliant to meet the various essential needs of life. In this sense, after the gap of 34 years in the year 2020, a New Education Policy (NEP-2020) has emerged to bring about a radical change in the education system that has been destroyed by the Corona epidemic, to get revival from the ashes like a bird. It is clearly observed from factual facets obtained from various secondary sources that is primary in nature that NEP-2020 on higher education; wishing away structural problems with the motive of wishing a magical solution. But in demands of 21st century knowledge-driven society and new milieu of the millennium, our education must look forward for incorporation of the changes taking place and addressing the issued in the curriculum to the intended beneficiaries to bring a viable economic, social, cultural, technological and after all environmental order in the country for realizing the constitutional goals and incredible philosophy of the great nation. This research paper has been designed with the motive of identifying the significance, strength, weaknesses, opportunities and threats of higher education programmes and implementation strategies proposed by NEP-2020 with special reference of Varanasi District with the purpose of why and what is the metaphysical ground behind the NEP-2020 and what are its pros and cons so far as societal relevance and quality magnitudes of higher education i.e. digital initiatives, quality mandate in research, innovation and development, physical and mental wellbeing programmes, the structure and lengths of degree programmes etc. are concerned. The primary objective of this research is to study the impact of NEP-2020 on higher institutions of Varanasi District in the light of Indian Knowledge System. This research is a quantitative and qualitative descriptive study and the data was then analyzed and reviewed to arrive at the inferences and conclusions.

Keywords: Indian Knowledge System, National education policy, Higher education, Transformation, Community, Literacy, Education & Skill, Innovation, Self-sustainable Workforce.

Introduction: "Creativity is as important now in education as literacy and we should treat it with the same status....." – Ken Robinson

As we know from the various literature reviews the NEP, 2020 recognizes the rich heritage of ancient and eternal Indian Knowledge and thought as a guiding principle. Various factual facets shows that the Indian Knowledge Systems comprise of Jnan, Vignan, and Jeevan Darshan that have evolved out of experience, observation, experimentation, and rigorous analysis. According to Albert Einstein; "We owe a lot to the ancient Indians, teaching us how to count. Without which most modern scientific discoveries would have been impossible." No doubt, today's knowledge-driven world is a competitive world full of undue anxiety and overstress. The role of administrators, academia, industry and Students at different levels play on the integrity, effectiveness and efficiency of the organization. In this way, we need to develop forward looking, responsive, world class higher educational institutions to prepare 21st century-ready students. We have to work to ensure access, inclusivity, equitability, affordability and quality in higher education. We must bring in a transformative education system rooted in Indian values, thoughts and sense of service. After all, the implementation of NEP 2020 should be seen as a transformative experience through which students and faculties can prepare themselves to succeed in the many and varied roles they

* Assistant Professor, Department of Economics Government Degree College, Jakkhini, Varanasi-221305

will undertake in future life. From the various literature cited, we can easily see that National Education Policy 2020 On July 29, 2020 was set forth by the Ministry of Human Resource Development; the new renamed Ministry of Education(MoE). This reformed policy has been put forward to reconstruct the Indian Education System. As we know that the last educational policy on education was formed in 1986. In this way, the main focus of NEP 2020 is to make education more inclusive, especially in a diverse country like India. But, the role of university and college departments Heads, Directors, and Administrators have the challenging task of managing resources within a complex environment of university policies and state and central regulations and should be held accountable and recognized for performance after implementation of NEP 2020. With the new energy and new confidence NEP-2020 gives us the direction and path for decolonizing our education and achieving aspirations, creating pride in our languages, culture and knowledge and the components of NEP-2020 such as Multi-modal education, Academic Bank of Credits, Multiple Entry-Exit, Skill Development will prove to be milestones in the direction of student first teacher led learning.

Objectives of NEP 2020 Implementation –

- (1) It focuses on Student's general development apart from their academic and educational growth.
- (2) The policy demands that students physical, psychological and emotional well-being be ensured by providing support facilities and Career Counsellors to all students.
- (3) It also focuses on inclusivity by promoting education in our country's local languages.
- (4) It emphasizes the importance of maximizing communication in all Indian languages for improved cognitive development and the learner's overall personality growth.
- (5) In-depth understanding of research and Innovation methodologies and critical thinking abilities with emphasis on out-of-the-box thinking.

In this concern the aim of the present study to find out whether the Educational Institutions of Varanasi District are able to implement the objectives set by the NEP, 2020 in their Teaching-learning Skills and also Co-curricular Techniques or not? Have the Skill development courses run by the government become a means of raising funds for the institutions or the students benefiting from these courses? In nut shell in our study we want to know about the NEP, 2020 in Higher education will be effective or not(with yes or no questions).

Hypothesis of the Study: In this context of above objectives the following hypothesis is formed:

H0: Implementation of NEP 2020 have no impact on learner's engagement or participation in Varanasi District.

H1: Implementation of NEP 2020 have significant impact on learner's engagement or participation in Varanasi District.

Research Methodology: A field Survey method was used to collect data from the sample. The study was conducted on a sample size of 110 college students including students of Graduate, Postgraduate and Doctoral degree. The responses for perceived challenges were recorded on a five-point continuum representing Strongly Agree, Agree, Undecided, Disagree, and Strongly Disagree with scores of 5, 4, 3, 2, and 1, respectively. The perceived challenges score of each respondents was calculated by adding up the scores obtained by respondents on all the items. So, the present Study on Implementation of NEP 2020 was carried out on the basis of Primary as well as Secondary data such as books, articles by various authors, data from several Websites, Journals etc. Available data which is reliable, suitable and adequate to the relevant research topic. Secondary data was collected to view past research so as to construct the research problem and primary data was conducted to find the views of students and faculties regarding their expectation and participation in skill & curricular and Co-curricular activities.

Limitations of the study:

- (1) This study is confined to mostly Varanasi District.
- (2) The study is restricted with the sample of 100 to 110 respondents.
- (3) Respondents biasness, time and cost are also constraint of the study.

(4) Questionnaire Considered was without Validity and Reliability Test.

(5) Study includes only few variables for analysis.

Data Analysis and Interpretation: Data collection is defined as a procedure of collecting, measuring and analyzing accurate insights for research using standard validated techniques. In this study, some of the tools used here are questionnaires, interview schedule, focus group discussion to the Students.

(A) Data generated by survey through questionnaire about effective implementation of NEP 2020 i.e. Awareness Level of soft skills possessed by Learners

Sr. No.	Soft skills after implementation of NEP 2020	Aware (Response in percentage)	Not Aware (Response in percentage)	Maybe (Response in percentage)
1.	Ability to communicating effectively, verbally and non-verbally	64	16	20
2.	Ability to work in a team as a team member	92	08	00
3.	Ability to make logical decisions	22	48	30
4.	Ability to face problems in a creative ways	19	71	10
5.	Ability to interact with people from different levels in a comfortable and friendly manner	48	52	00
6.	Ability to motivate and influence other towards achievement of organizational goals	28	72	00
7.	Ability to plan project timelines and meet deadlines	64	34	02
8.	Ability to follow moral values	42	54	04
9.	Ability to handle and tolerate professional stress	60	38	02
10.	Ability to be committed to organizational goals	28	66	06
11.	Ability to plan and organize events and activities	38	48	14

Source: Field-survey

(B) Data generated by survey through Questionnaire after implementation of NEP 2020 regarding awareness of types of appropriate teaching methods and tools which is teachers use during teaching-learning process within Distance learning students & Non-distance learning students.

S.No.	Variables	Frequency(f) of Distance learning Students (N=100)	Percentage(%) of Distance learning Students (N=100)	Frequency(f) of Non-distance learning students (N=100)	Percentage(%) of Non-distance learning students (N=100)
1.	Lecture	76	76.0	92	92.0
2.	Group Presentation	96	96.0	98	98.0
3.	Question & Answer	96	96.0	94	94.0
4.	Discussion	87	87.0	94	94.0

5.	Assignment	98	98.0	0	0
6.	Visual Aids	94	94.0	96	96.0
7.	Face-to-Face Session	94	94.0	96	96.0
8.	Role Play	98	98.0	96	96.0
9.	Demonstration	0	0	90	90.0
10.	Project	96	96.0	98	98.0
11.	On-line Activities	98	98.0	92	92.0
12.	Watching	98	98.0	0	0
13.	Dramatization	96	96.0	94	94.0
14.	Child Centered	0	0	96	96.0
15.	Teacher centered	0	0	92	92.0

* Field-survey

(C) Perceived Challenges of National Education Policy, 2020 by college students of Varanasi District.

S. No.	Items	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly disagree
		Frequency	Frequency	Frequency	Frequency	Frequency
1.	Lack of infrastructure and transportation facilities	39	57	10	04	0
2.	Corruption in the education sector	48	38	14	05	05
3.	Lack of optimum funds	38	50	12	08	02
4.	Disparity Between rural and urban areas in manpower and quality of education	37	52	11	07	03
5.	Fear of commercialization and Privatization	38	51	12	08	01
6.	Policy framing by central government	32	55	15	6	2
7.	Universal access to education	31	60	10	8	2
8.	Vocational education	20	60	20	5	5
9.	Focus on regional languages	27	40	20	12	11
10.	Undermining English language	22	43	24	10	11
11.	Overburden of syllabus	11	43	31	10	15

Findings, Results & Discussion: From the above table (A), it can be summarized that after

implementation of NEP 2020 Soft skills graduates are not aware that needs improvement and tools available to improve the quality of soft skills in learners. From the analysis of table (B), We can easily see that the table give an indication that students are familiar with some types of methods that teachers/ lecturers employ in their teaching-learning processes. Different frequencies, different percentage shows positive responses of students of distance and non-distance learning students. But the matter of concern that, as we know that three main key determinants of quality in higher education are the adequate availability of quality faculty, optimum and adequate infrastructure and resources and availability of third-party quality. In this case, When the above hypothesis is tested at 5%LOS, then we get, P Value=0.031, Since $p=0.031 < 0.05$, therefore Null hypothesis is Rejected and Alternative hypothesis will be accepted. Evidences shows that including the Banaras Hindu University all the Government, Aided and Self-finance Colleges in Varanasi, Uttar Pradesh has constituted a panel to discuss student's engagement in various university/college activities to promote their overall development rather than just focusing on academic growth. During this survey all the administrators related to institution states positively that the panel will identify opportunities and activities when students may be effectively and proactively engaged and aims to enhance the university's/college's ecosystem in curricular and co-curricular activities. It will suggest ways to help students adapt to the university's/college's environment and determine means to execute reform measures to help students. Many institutions are adopting new and best practices. The issue of recruitment, construction, grading and assessment must be dealt with effectively and we should provide facilities to students in their proximity. From the table(c) data revealed that 'Lack of infrastructure and transportation facilities and 'corruption in the education sector' were perceived as major challenges with weighted mean score approximately 4.00 and ranked 1st and followed by 'lack of optimum funds' ranked 2nd with weighted mean score approximately 3.99. The 'Disparity between rural and urban areas in manpower and quality of education' received weighted mean approximately 3.90 with rank 3rd followed by fear of commercialization and privatization. Policy framing by central and state government, universal access to education, vocational education, focus on regional languages, undermining English languages, overburden of syllabus with weighted mean scores approximately 3.94, 3.90, 3.84, 3.76, 3.60, 3.42, 3.20 ranked 4th, 5th, 6th, 7th, 8th, 9th, and 10th respectively.

Thus, in reality during the field-survey of this study at the grass-root level it was found that in Varanasi District while majority of students in higher education go to universities and colleges which come under the state system, they lack adequate resources in terms of manpower and infrastructure and there is no world class study material available in our own languages. In such a situation, the NEP 2020 looks like 'Old Wine in a New Bottle'; where instead of working on the grass-root level, special attention is being given to paperwork and has been facing challenges in ensuring that the quality of teaching and learning takes place effectively.

Conclusions and Recommendation : Despite these facts it should be said in fairness that through the effective implementation of NEP 2020 in Varanasi District it was observed that Skill Development Courses & Co-curricular activities like; Chakravayuh (a confluence of the finest brains), Corporate Social Responsibility (Blood Donation Drive, Yoga camp, Eye Check-up Camp, Social Entrepreneurship, Exhibition of Handicrafts made by handicap students, Road Safety Campaign, Self Defense, Sexual Harassment Cautions, Guest lectures/Workshops/Seminars/Webinars, Industrial Inputs (Industrial tours and visits), Leadership Study Centre, Recreational Centre, Storm (Intercollegiate case study competition), Synergy (Networking between peer, faculty and alumni) etc. cater to the development of a student's entire personality, draw out the latent powers of students of different temperaments, complement academic work and develop social & civic sense. Without these activities students would be mere book-worms. According to Marilyn Andrews "Skills development should be embedded in academic programmes, rather than an add-on, to give students the best chance of shaping their future."

At last but not the least, Some suggestions for improving of effective implementation of NEP-2020 i.e. Need for review of Course Content, Diversification, New courses, etc; Proliferation of Courses,

Sisterhood programmes, Effective Industry-Institution Collaboration, Improvement of teaching methods, Integration of practical training with the Institutional Courses, Simplification of procedures, Clarity in Responsibilities, Committee Management, Effective Leadership, Role of other Stakeholders in Quality Enhancement, Transforming learning landscape through Career Focussed Initiatives, Effective placement cell, Effective Innovation and Entrepreneurship cell, Skill Centre, and Social Audit process of policy implementation should be executed at grass-root level. To ensure holistic and multidisciplinary education with the flexibility and mobility envisioned in NEP-2020, we need to put in place multiple facilities such as: A broad framework of qualifications with consistency across programmes under National Higher Education Qualifications Framework (NHEQF), Academic Bank of Credits, Guidelines for multidisciplinary education provisions for multiple entry and exit, provision to earn credits in a blended mode i.e. through different modes such as physical, ODL/ and online, creation of degree+ digital platform providing opportunities to have courses of choice other than their core disciplines, providing co-location of industries in campus by establishing research and development units through industry connect, flexibility in education should be provided in which glimpses of everything is provided to the students in first year and they are given a chance to choose their own discipline subsequently etc. Now the question arises in this concern that if the Government knows every disease, then who will bell the Cat? It will not be only by implementing the policies, the Government's attention is also expected towards its better and effective implementation.

Scope of Further Research:

1. This study was limited to Varanasi District thus giving an opportunity to other researchers to focus on other demographic parts of the India.
2. Increasing number of variables and the sample size for the further research may also lead to new dimensions/interpretation of quality so that the error factor may be less than 23.60%.
3. Future studies to investigate technologies to be invented in NEP, 2020.
4. Future research to examine the quality of teaching techniques.
5. In future research more research is needed to apply and test the educational structure and policy.
6. Therefore, future research should be conducted in more realistic settings to betterment of student's community.

References:

1. <http://www.gyanunlimited.com/education/co-curricular-activities-meaning-definition-examples-importance-benefits/2437/>
2. www.academia.edu
3. Quality Approaches in Higher Education, Vol.3, No.1, 2012, ISSN 2161-265X.
4. Competitiveness, FICCI Higher Education Summit.(2014)
5. M.R.Kurup, "Quality and Excellence in Higher Education".
6. Doherty, D.Geoffrey, "Developing Quality System in Education."
7. <https://skillsuccess.blogspot.in/>
8. M.S.Rao,(2010) Soft Skills Enhancing Employability: Connecting Campus with Corporate. I.K. International Pvt. Ltd. Publishers.
9. <https://www.education.gov.in/>
10. Anonymous, All India Survey on Higher Education. Available at www.mhrd.gov.in